

REAL TIME UAV 3D PATH PLANNING USING INTEGRATED PROBABILISTIC PATTERN MODELLING**¹Sushma Uday Kamat, ²Krupa Rasane**¹Research Scholar, VTU , Belagavi-590014²Professor, Dept. of ECE, JCE Belagavi -590014

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ABSTRACT: Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) are utilized for a wide range of tasks, such as search, traffic monitoring, package delivery, military combat engagements and rescue operations. In each of these situations, the UAV is used to independently navigate the environment without human involvement, perform out particular tasks while avoiding obstacles, and collect data. To avoid the traffic for delivery service, some of them using the Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) to deliver the products. In collaborative control systems for unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), path planning is an important study field. UAV path planning is the process of looking for a route which will enable a UAV to follow a better flight path from its beginning point and eventually return at its destination point within the context of a particular mission. This flight path must fit the UAV's limitations while avoiding obstacles and aggressive threats. Thus, effective path planning is necessary to achieve traffic free delivery of services. Planning a practical three-dimensional (3-D) flight plan for unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) is a significant problem for following management and decision making. Hence in this work, Multi-Doped Pattern Learning (MDPL) Based Real Time 3D Path Planning of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles Using Integrated Probabilistic Pattern Modelling (IPPM) is presented. This approach will optimally find the correlation between the vertices from different sensor data and map with the pattern modelling to form 3D visual effect which helps to drive the UAV and prevent from accident by obstacles.

KEYWORDS: Unmanned Aerial Vehicles, Multi-Doped Pattern Learning, Integrated Probabilistic Pattern Modeling.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the usage of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) for military and civilian missions such intelligence collection, surveillance, reconnaissance, Suppression of Enemy Air Defenses (SEAD), search and rescue, and goods delivery has increased. A common and long-term topic among such missions is the development of an intelligent system that enables UAVs to conduct tasks autonomously without human intervention.

[2].

Unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) networks are one of the technologies that are frequently brought up during discussions of smart city scenarios [3]. Data gathering from sensor nodes in urban scenarios is highly convenient due to the extensive deployment of communication base cable networks, stations and so on. A sensor node can send data through a base station and to a data center in IoT applications.

An unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) is one of the most logical solutions for collecting data in areas that are difficult to access, such as deserts and oceans.

There are several uses for autonomous unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), all of which require efficient path planning technique. The main mission considers the navigation constraints, such as avoiding obstacles and flying time constraints. Area Coverage Path Planning (CPP) and Data Harvesting (DH) from Internet of Things sensors are examples of these applications. Most autonomous unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) path planning techniques are created for a single type of mission [4]. Particularly soon will come the development of techniques that allow an unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) to fly autonomously from arbitrary starting places to destinations while avoiding obstacles in dynamic, unknown territory.

There are uses of UAVs, including search and rescue and terrain mapping. Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) represent a promising as a solution because they allow multiple UAVs to automatically collect data along a path that was not possible before. However, the quantity and energy used by UAVs will increase without a properly thought path. As a result, the multi-UAV local path minimizes the number of UAV is necessary while optimizing its path, which is critical for efficient data collecting. [5]. Autonomous path planning can guarantee mission completion in many mission scenarios. Because of the UAV's high maneuverability and the task space's continuity, conventional procedures are useless as control strategies [9].

A significant problem with UAV flight safety is path planning. UAV path planning under a specified mission background is the method of searching a path that allows a better flight path for the UAV from the starting point to the target. This flight path should avoid obstacles and enemy threats while respecting the UAV's limitations. UAV route planning is a significant feature of modern warfare with the air defense technology for improving UAV efficiency and conducting out long-range accurate combat strikes. However, due to the limitations involved in UAV path planning, as well as considerations and an imperfect task background, the present UAV path planning methods have practical flaws, requiring the discussion and development of an accurate and effective algorithm of UAV path planning. [10].

There are several other methods developed to route the UAV in proper direction and along with the obstacle prediction. Even by using the deep learning method of machine learning concept, it requires a greater number of training features to improve the accuracy of predicting the traffic flow in a road of an area. This will increase the time complexity due to analysing of a greater number of database and thereby increasing the space complexity.

Hence to overcome these issues, Multi-Doped Pattern Learning (MDPL) based real time 3D path planning of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles using Integrated Probabilistic Pattern Modelling (IPPM) is presented. The remaining work is analysed as follows: the literature survey is described by the section **II**. The section III presents the methodology. The section IV demonstrates the result analysis of presented approach. Finally, the work is concluded in section V.

II. LITEARATURE SURVEY

Ujjwal Verma, Arsh Tangri et. al., [1] compare the use of texture classifiers and deep learning techniques to identify regions that have recently flooded in UAV aerial pictures. In this study, comparison of the performance of flooded/non-flooded images using deep learning techniques and traditional hand-crafted feature-based classifiers is carried out. This prompts the use of textural features created by the researchers. The FloodNet dataset, which includes images of Hurricane Harvey, is considered to evaluate conventional and deep learning algorithms. For the flooded class, the F1 score for the LBP texture classifier was 0.84 and 0.87 for the self-supervised deep learning strategy. This discovery demonstrates that a texture-based classifier built by hand can compare with deep learning approaches.

Yingsheng Peng, Yong Liu, and Han Zhang et. al., [6] UAV-Assisted Edge Computing Network Path Planning with Deep Reinforcement Learning in an edge computing network with a UAV, edge server, and multiple devices offloading computing tasks, they analyze the path planning problem with deep reinforcement learning to handle with the gradual development of the complex environment, an online optimal path based on the Double Deep Q-learning Network is developed using the deep reinforcement learning (DRL) method (DDQN). Numerous simulation results show the DRL-based path planning algorithm's usefulness in terms of system rewards and fast convergence.

Miles Krusniak, Keaton Leppanen, Tang, Fan Gao, Yizhen Wang, Yi Shang et. al., [11] The algorithm is described as "A Detection Confidence-Regulated Path Planning (DCRPP) Algorithm for Improved Small Object Counting in Aerial Images." They increase with an altitude shifting path planner, UAV data is collected while maintaining energy consumption while optimizing deep learning-based object detection confidences. Given energy restrictions, UAV altitude is modified by the adaptable path planner ("DCRPP") utilizing an actual altitude confidence connection, resulting in better quality data. In our conservation-focused simulation, DCRPP achieves 11.92% higher accuracy than fixed-height techniques.

Gyeong Taek Lee and Chang Ouk Kim et. al., [12] presents Autonomous Control of Combat Unmanned Aerial Vehicles to Evade Surface-to-Air Missiles Using Deep Reinforcement Learning, choosing the easiest path, and flying in formation. By amplifying the imitation effect, they create a reinforcement learning system that allows more exploration. The combination of the random network distillation and self imitation learning techniques in terms of learning stability and convergence speed in both experiments, the suggested method outperformed the already used algorithms.

Juaren Steigery, Ning Luy, Sameh Sorour et. al., [14] demonstrates the learning of path planning and coverage mapping in UAV-aided emergency communications. The possibility of a rotary wing UAV behaves as an aerial base station has been taken account. It would provide surveillance for an area in need of emergency communication services but with an unknown and irregular user distribution. The path planning and coverage mapping issues is resolved online using a deep learning model. This is recommended. The authors also highlight the connection between and competing objectives of path planning and coverage mapping, but they demonstrate through Monte Carlo simulation that, with the

appropriate parameters, the method can address both issues.

Micro Theile, Harald Bayerlein, Richard Nai, David Gesbert, and Marco Caccamo et. al., [15] discusses Deep Reinforcement Learning and Changing Power Constraints for UAV Coverage Path Planning. A novel technique for directing a webcam unmanned aerial aircraft (UAV) on a CPP mission with several landing options in an area with no-fly zones and random start locations They trained a double deep Q-network to match the UAV's limited power cost and coverage objective (DDQN). The recommended method can be used in a variety of situations and combines complex goal structures with system limits.

Han Qie, Dianxi Shi, Tianlong Shen, Xinhai Xu, Yuan Li, Liuqing Wang et. al., [17] The use of multi-agent reinforcement learning for multi-UAV target distribution and path planning is discussed in this paper. Using a multi-agent reinforcement learning system known as the multi-agent deep deterministic policy gradient (MADDPG) technology, concurrent target assignment and path planning is made possible (STAPP). The MADDPG framework is employed to train the system to manage objective allocation and route planning problems while also applying a reward structure. The presented system can successfully deal with changing scenarios because its execution only requires the positions of the UAVs, targets, and threat zones. Because the system's neural network is simple, real-time performance is assured.

Ursula Challita, Walid Saad, and Christian Bettstetter et. al., [18] A Deep a Reinforcement Learning Approach to Cellular-Connected UAV Interference Management is presented. The approach for designing a system of cellular-connected unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) path with consideration for interfering is described in this study. With the objective of decreasing a series of time-dependent utility functions, the deep ESN (Echo State Network) architecture shown here is trained to enable each UAV to map each view of network state to an action. The results also showed that the ideal UAV altitude varies with ground network density and UE data rate demands, and that it is crucial for reducing interference levels on ground UEs and the wireless transmission delay of the UAV.

III. MULTI-DOPED PATTERN LEARNING (MDPL) BASED REAL TIME 3D PATH PLANNING OF UNMANNED AERIAL VEHICLES

In this section, Multi-Doped Pattern Learning (MDPL) based real time 3D path planning of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles using Integrated Probabilistic Pattern Modeling (IPPM) is demonstrated. The main objective of the presented model is i) To collect the dataset based on multiple sensors to locate the drone in the region of driving area; ii) To implement a multi-class classification model using Multi-Doped Pattern Learning (MDPL) which is to predict the directionality according to sensor data, iii) To enhance the accuracy of prediction system and iv) To reconstruct the predicted data to form 3D visualization for the range in the area and assist for routing plan using Integrated Probabilistic Pattern Modeling (IPPM).

The block diagram of MDPL based real time 3D path planning of UAV using IPPM is shown Fig. 1. In this approach own obstacles are created to represent the data. There are several difficulties in

complex locations, including such as urban, semi urban or rural. Only a small number of cylindrical obstructions can wrap around different-shaped barriers. Despite the fact this approach should lead to a more conservative solution to the path planning problem, the obstacle is viewed as numerous cylindrical obstacle zones of indefinite height to ensure flight safety and the convenience of the plan method. All through the course of the flight, all UAVs should always remain outside the obstacle area.

The input parameters are considered and are initialized. The feature vectors play a vital role in classification. The feature vector is a list of numerical attributes of observable phenomena. It reflects the features that are given into a deep learning model that makes a prediction. Humans can make choices based on qualitative data analysis. The feature index value is selected based on the feature dataset. The selected feature index is applied to feature vector.

Algorithm:

- Input: Map Coordinate Position $I\{x_0, y_0, z_0\}$, ultrasonic feature F_t
- Output: Path Pattern P_T and coordinate positions, $P\{x, y, z\}$
- Initialize particles G_p and node vector N_v .

Initialize iteration count, $iter = 0$.

- While ($iter$)
- Update the node (x, y, z) position with random allocation.
- $Node_x = X_{min} + ((X_{max} - X_{min}) \times (\frac{rand}{2}))$
- $Node_y = Y_{min} + ((Y_{max} - Y_{min}) \times (\frac{rand}{2}))$
- $Node_z = Z_{min} + ((Z_{max} - Z_{min}) \times (\frac{rand}{2}))$
- If $(I(x_0, y_0, z_0) < Node(x, y, z))$, then
- Update $Node'(x, y, z) = Node(x + 1, y + 1, z + 1) \times rand$
- Iter++
- End If
- End 'iter' loop
- For $i = 0$ to size (I) loop

To find the difference of coordinates.

- $\Delta_x = Node_x \sim Node_{x-1}$
- $\Delta_y = Node_y \sim Node_{y-1}$
- $\Delta_z = Node_z \sim Node_{z-1}$

To Estimate the distance and velocity of movement

- $Dist_{xy} = \sqrt{\Delta_x^2 + \Delta_y^2}$

- $Dist_{yz} = \sqrt{\Delta_y^2 + \Delta_z^2}$
- $Dist_{xz} = \sqrt{\Delta_x^2 + \Delta_z^2}$
- $Velocity = \frac{Dist_{xyz} - Dist_{xyz}^F}{t}$
- Where, $Dist_{xyz}$ and $Dist_{xyz}^F$ are the distance of current and previous time instant.
- t – Time taken to travel at each instant
- If $((Dist_{xy} < Dist_{max}) \ \&\& \ (Dist_{yz} < Dist_{max}) \ \&\& \ (Dist_{xz} < Dist_{max}))$, then
 - $waypoint(i) = \{Node_x, Node_y, Node_z\}$
 - Predict Obstacles in the path from ‘ F_t ’
 - $Pos_i = F_t(x, y, z) \sim Max(F_v(x, y, z))$
 - $waypoint'(i) = waypoint(i) \sim Pos_i$
 - If $(waypoint(i) > safe_{Point})$, then
 - $waypoint(i) = waypoint(i) - waypoint'(i)$
 - If $(Velocity > safe_{Velocity})$, then
 - Reduce $Velocity$ until $(waypoint(i) < Pos_i)$
 - Update drone (x, y, z)
 - Continue loop
 - End If
 - End If
 - End If
 - Path Pattern, $P_T = \{waypoint(i), F_t(i)\}$
 - $P\{x, y, z\} = waypoint(i)\{x, y, z\}$
 - Update coordinate position of drone.
 - End loop ‘x’

In this approach, to improve the performance of the UAV routing system, the optimal data modeling is used to predict the directionality and pattern-based vertices modeling for the 3D pattern representation of the predicted location. MDPL method is used to reduce the number of iterations for data learning that are collected from the different sensors. This is processed by the hybridization of enhanced deep learning with multiple pattern-based feature representation to achieve the prediction performance of routing system and the directionality validation to drive UAV.

MDPL is a method for identifying regularities and similarities in data. These similarities can now be found using statistical analysis, historical data, or knowledge gathered by the machine itself. A pattern is a repeating problem in the real world or in abstract ideas.

The advantages of the MDPL algorithms are

- It can process any kind of data in both pre and post processing stages.
- It is hybridization of enhanced deep learning with multiple pattern-based feature representation.
- It can also Represent the 3D structure of the video frames based on depth prediction and sensor-based data.

Fig. 1: Block diagram of MDPL based Real Time 3D Path Planning of UAV using IPPM

Based on the MDPL classification, weight values are estimated. If the weight is greater than 1 then update is done, and updates are again applied to weight value estimation process to reduce the weights for effective virtual path visualization. If the weights are less than 1 then the path of routing and 3D visualization are provided using IPPM method.

$$\text{Bayes Rule } P\left(\frac{y}{x}\right) = \frac{p\left(\frac{x}{y}\right)p(y)}{p(x)} \quad (1)$$

Here x defines the variable or feature value, and y is the target variable. Where $p(y)$ is the prior probability without observing x data, $p(x)$ is independent on y and (x/y) is the likelihood of function. The maximum posterior probability is expressed as

$$y_{\text{map}} = \text{argmax}_y p\left(\frac{y}{x}\right) = \text{argmax}_y \frac{p\left(\frac{x}{y}\right)p(y)}{p(x)} \quad (2)$$

Where argmax defines maximum arguments of y . the uniform prior distributions are

$$y_{\text{ML}} = \text{argmax}_y p\left(\frac{x}{y}\right) \quad (3)$$

Where y_{ML} is the maximum likelihood of y . Based on these values the IPPM plan the UAV path. 3D path visualization is a valuable tool for gaining a qualitative understanding of UAV path planning. This can further represent as the 3D structure of the image frames based on different depth prediction and the sensor-based validation using Integrated Probabilistic Pattern Modeling (IPPM) technique.

IV. RESULT ANALYSIS

In this section, Multi-Doped Pattern Learning based real time 3D path planning of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles using Integrated Probabilistic Pattern Modeling is demonstrated. The result analysis of

presented approach is discussed here. In this analysis real time obstacles are created with random sizes. After the implementation of functionality, firstly trajectory optimization model is started. Then this analysis finds the convergence line then travelling path is plotted. The travel path will be plotted after Parameters initialisation. i.e., The Fitness value should reach the maximum value and it reaches the maximum value then it will be stopped). The default maximum fitness value is 1200.

Fig. 2: The 3D Projection of UAV Path and Obstacles

In the fig. 2 the red circles represent different real time obstacles. The travel path is shown with blue color. The travel path automatically stops when it reaches the maximum fitness. When obstacle is encountered dynamically after UAV has started the flight, then it optimally travels in reverse direction or changes the direction. In the Fig. 2 the 2D view of y and z direction is displayed.

Fig. 3: Different Travelling Paths of UAV

To vary the path of travelling, three different parameters (u, v and w) are introduced, and these parameters are updated by weight value. The weight value always converges to 0 or less than the value compared to previous value. According to the deviations from obstacle to the UAV, and the selections of sources decides the travelling path. The travelling path is stopped when it reaches the destination.

Fig. 4: Overall Value

In fig. 4 the V represents the overall value for the iteration. Compared to v and w, the travelling path of w is less compared to the the previous value (i.e., a reduced convergences).

Fig. 5: Travelling paths of u' , v' , w' Parameters

The $u'v'$ and w' are the iterations from the next/updated instant.

Fig. 6: Updated Travelling Paths

In fig. 5 and 6, u, v and w are the previous and u' v' and w' are the updated positions. The Fig. 7 shows the graph for τ

Fig. 6: Cost function(τ) Graph

The object/cost function, should be represented by τ (i.e., Cost value). In the same way the Fig. 7 represents the γ and is the related weight value.

Fig. 8: Graph for γ

Whenever the UAV changes the direction, the velocity will be reduced. γ is inversely proportional to the velocity.

Fig. 9: Graphs fo τ, γ, ϕ

ϕ is the angle of UAV i.e., the degree of UAV with respect to its path that it travels in. After the collection of all features, confusion matrix is formed. The four possible outcomes of confusion matrix are (True Positive), True Negative (TN), False Positive (FP), and False Negative (FN) and the parameters like accuracy, Precision, Recall and f1-score are obtained using these parameters.

Accuracy: The capacity of the framework to precisely characterize information depends to a vast degree on the illustrations provided.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FN + FP} \dots (4)$$

Precision also called positive predicted value is the fraction of significant instances among the retrieved instances.

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \dots (2)$$

Recall also known as sensitivity or True Positive Rate (TPR) is the fraction of significant instances that have been retrieved over the total amount of relevant instances.

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \dots (5)$$

F1 score or F-measure is a measure of a test's accuracy for binary classification.

$$F1 - Score = 2 * \frac{Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall} \dots (6)$$

The table 1 shows the evaluation of performance metrics.

Table 1: Evaluation of Performance Metrics with different Methods

Performance Metrics	Decision Tree (DT)	Bi-directional Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)	Presented MDPL Approach
Accuracy	0.92	0.96	0.97
Avg. Recall	0.92	0.97	0.97
Avg. precision	0.94	0.98	0.99
Avg. F1-score	0.93	0.97	0.98

Compared to two different approaches i.e., DT and Bi-LSTM, presented approach has better results in terms of accuracy, avg. recall, avg. precision and avg. f1-score. The Fig. 10 shows the performance comparison between presented MDPL approach and other earlier approaches in terms of accuracy and recall.

Fig. 10: Performance Evaluation in terms of Accuracy and Avg. Recall

In fig. 10 the x-axis represents different methods of UAV 3D path planning and y-axis represents the performance values. Proposed MDPL based approach has high accuracy and Avg. recall in comparison with Bi-LSTM. The Fig. 11 shows the avg. precision and avg. f1-score metrics performance comparison of different methods.

Fig. 11: Comparative Graph for Avg. precision and Avg. F1-score

In fig. 11 illustrates the Comparative Graph for Avg. precision and Avg. F1-score. Hence the Multi-Doped Pattern Learning based real time 3D path planning of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles using Integrated Probabilistic Pattern Modeling has effectively obtained a 3D path planning for UAV which is the shortest route.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, Multi-Doped Pattern Learning based real time 3D path planning of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles using Integrated Probabilistic Pattern Modelling is implemented. A multi-class classification model namely Multi-Doped Pattern Learning (MDPL) is used to predict the directionality based on the sensor data. Integrated Probabilistic Pattern Modelling (IPPM) is used for the reconstruction of predicted data to form 3D visualization in the area and assist the same in routing plan range. Different obstacles are created with random sizes to represent the data. The travel paths of UAV with different parameters are plotted and in addition plotted the graphs for the parameters like τ, γ, ϕ . Using the confusion matrix parameters, the performance metrics like Accuracy, avg.

Recall, avg. Precision and avg. F1-score are measured. The performance of presented MDPL and IPPM based approach is compared with earlier DT and Bi-LSTM approach. However, the MDPL based approach has better results than the earlier approach. Hence presented approach has effectively obtained the real time 3D path planning of UAV. Thereby UAV is prevented from colliding with obstacles.

VI. REFERENCES

- [1] Ujjwal Verma, Arsh Tangri, “Comparison of Texture Classifiers with Deep Learning Methods for Flooded Region Identification in UAV Aerial Images”, IGARSS 2022 - 2022 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium, **DOI:** 10.1109/IGARSS46834.2022.9884718
- [2] WAN Kaifang, LI Bo, GAO Xiaoguang, HU Zijian, and YANG Zhipeng, “A learning-based flexible autonomous motion control method for UAV in dynamic unknown environments”, *Journal of Systems Engineering and Electronics*, Vol. 32, No. 6, December 2021, pp.1490 – 1508
- [3] Won Joon Yun, Yoo Jeong Ha, Soyi Jung, Joongheon Kim, “Autonomous Aerial Mobility Learning for Drone-Taxi Flight Control”, 2021 International Conference on Information and Communication Technology Convergence (ICTC), **DOI:** 10.1109/ICTC52510.2021.9620751
- [4] Mirco Theile, Harald Bayerlein, Richard Nai, David Gesbert, Marco Caccamo, “UAV Path Planning using Global and Local Map Information with Deep Reinforcement Learning”, 2021 20th International Conference on Advanced Robotics (ICAR), **DOI:** 10.1109/ICAR53236.2021.9659413
- [5] Yuwen Pan, Yuanwang Yang and Wenzao Li, “A Deep Learning Trained by Genetic Algorithm to Improve the Efficiency of Path Planning for Data Collection With Multi-UAV”, *IEEE Access* (Volume: 9), 2021, **DOI:** 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3049892
- [6] Yingsheng Peng, Yong Liu, and Han Zhang, “Deep Reinforcement Learning based Path Planning for UAV-assisted Edge Computing Networks”, 2021 IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC), 978-1-7281-9505-6/20, 2021 IEEE, **DOI:** 10.1109/WCNC49053.2021.9417292
- [7] Mrinmoy Sarkar, Xuyang Yan Shamila Nateghi, Bruce J. Holmes, Kyriakos G. Vamvoudakis, and Abdollah Homaifar, “A Framework for Testing and Evaluation of Operational Performance of Multi-UAV Systems”, *Conference Paper 2021*, Springer, doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-82193-7_24
- [8] Mirela Kundid Vasić; Ahmad Drak; Nediljko Bugarin; Stanko Kružić; Josip Musić; Christoph Pomrehn; Maximilian Schöbel; Maximilian Jochenek, Ivo Stančić, Vladan Papić, Rainer Herpers “Deep Semantic Image Segmentation for UAV-UGV Cooperative Path Planning: A Car Park Use Case”, 2020 International Conference on Software, Telecommunications and Computer Networks (SoftCOM), **DOI:** 10.23919/SoftCOM50211.2020.9238313
- [9] Yibing Li, Sitong Zhang, Fang Ye, Tao Jiang, Yingsong Li, “A UAV Path Planning Method Based on Deep Reinforcement Learning”, : 2020 IEEE USNC-CNC-URSI North American Radio Science Meeting (Joint with AP-S Symposium), **DOI:** 10.23919/USNC/URSI49741.2020.9321625
- [10] Jiaxuan Fan, Zhenya Wang, Jinlei Ren, Ying Lu, Yiheng Liu, “UAV online path planning technology based on deep reinforcement learning”, 2020 Chinese Automation Congress (CAC), 978-1-7281-7687-1/20, 2020 IEEE, **DOI:** 10.1109/CAC51589.2020.9327752

- [11] Miles Krusniak, Keaton Leppanen, Zhicheng Tang; Fan Gao, Yizhen Wang, Yi Shang, “A Detection Confidence-Regulated Path Planning (DCRPP) Algorithm for Improved Small Object Counting in Aerial Images”, 2020 IEEE International Conference on Consumer Electronics (ICCE), **DOI:** 10.1109/ICCE46568.2020.9043152
- [12] Gyeong Taek Lee And Chang Ouk Kim, “Autonomous Control of Combat Unmanned Aerial Vehicles to Evade Surface-to-Air Missiles Using Deep Reinforcement Learning”, IEEE Access (Volume: 8), 2020, **DOI:** 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3046284
- [13] Runjia Wu, Fangqing Gu, Jie Huang, “A multi-critic deep deterministic policy gradient UAV path planning”, 2020 16th International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Security (CIS), 978-1-6654-0445-7/20, 2020 IEEE, DOI: 10.1109/CIS52066.2020.00010
- [14] Juaren Steigery, Ning Luy, Sameh Sorour, “Learning for Path Planning and Coverage Mapping in UAV-Assisted Emergency Communications”, GLOBECOM 2020 - 2020 IEEE Global Communications Conference, 978-1-7281-8298-8/20, 2020 IEEE, DOI: 10.1109/GLOBECOM42002.2020.9322190
- [15] Mirco Theile, Harald Bayerlein, Richard Nai, David Gesbert, and Marco Caccamo, “UAV Coverage Path Planning under Varying Power Constraints using Deep Reinforcement Learning”, 2020 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS), October 25-29, 2020, Las Vegas, NV, USA (Virtual), DOI: 10.1109/IROS45743.2020.9340934
- [16] J. Xie, L. R. G. Carrillo and L. Jin, “Path planning for UAV to cover multiple separated convex polygonal regions”, *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 51770_51785, 2020
- [17] Han Qie, Dianxi Shi, Tianlong Shen, Xinhai Xu, Yuan Li, Liuqing Wang, “Joint Optimization of Multi-UAV Target Assignment and Path Planning Based on Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning”, IEEE Access (Volume: 7), 2019, **DOI:** 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2943253
- [18] Ursula Challita, Walid Saad, and Christian Bettstetter, “Interference Management for Cellular-Connected UAVs: A Deep Reinforcement Learning Approach”, IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications, 1536-1276, 2019 IEEE, doi: 10.1109/TWC.2019.2900035
- [19] Alonica Villanueva, Arnel Fajardo, “Deep Reinforcement Learning with Noise Injection for UAV Path Planning”, 2019 6th IEEE International Conference on Engineering Technologies and Applied Sciences (ICETAS)
- [20] Z. Zhang, J. X. Li, and J. Wang, “Sequential convex programming for nonlinear optimal control problems in UAV path planning”, *Aerosp. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 76, pp. 280_290, May 2018.